

Abstract

The immune system and the central nervous system represent two of the most fundamental systems of the human body, whose functions are essential for maintaining homeostasis and survival. The presence of neurotransmitter receptors on immune cells raises questions about potential underlying communication between these two systems and the possible effects this interaction may exert.

Based on this premise, the present review first focuses on the existence of neural connections between the central nervous system and primary or secondary lymphoid organs. It then analyzes the expression of norepinephrine and acetylcholine receptors in each immune cell subset, as well as experimental data derived from studies investigating the influence of these neurotransmitters on immune functions. Finally, it presents findings from studies demonstrating the disease-modifying properties of these neurotransmitters—or receptor agonists—on multiple sclerosis and its experimental model, experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE).

Introduction

The immune system represents one of the most crucial defense and regulatory mechanisms in living organisms. Its functions include protecting the host from the invasion and proliferation of potentially pathogenic microorganisms, eliminating neoplastic cells, promoting tissue remodeling following acute injury, and performing other functions that are either already known or remain to be discovered.

The primary tools that enable these functions are immune cells, which develop in several anatomical sites of the human body—most notably in the bone marrow, thymus, lymph nodes, and spleen. The front line of defense consists of cells of the innate immune system (neutrophils, macrophages, dendritic cells, and natural killer cells), which are activated first upon pathogen invasion and exert broad destructive actions that initiate the inflammatory response. Subsequently, the adaptive immune cells—T and B lymphocytes—take over, mounting highly specific cytotoxic or antibody-mediated responses targeting pathogenic microorganisms and infected cells, while sparing healthy tissues. Resolution of the immune response is ultimately mediated by a specialized subset of T lymphocytes known as regulatory T cells (Tregs).

However, this process does not always proceed ideally. Excessive or misdirected immune activation can lead to autoimmune conditions, characterized by immune attacks against the body's own tissues, whereas insufficient activation may result in oncogenesis or chronic inflammation [1].

Equally vital to survival is the nervous system. Through an extensive network of afferent and efferent fibers distributed throughout the body, the nervous system maintains real-time awareness of the organism's physiological and pathological status, as well as its environmental conditions. On this basis, it regulates both autonomic and voluntary functions to preserve homeostasis and ensure protection. A simple example is that exposure to heat activates sweat glands to cool the body (an automatic response) while simultaneously motivating the individual to seek a cooler environment (a conscious response).

These two essential systems—the nervous and the immune—are interconnected and engage in bidirectional communication. A classical pathway of such interaction is the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis, which culminates in corticosteroid release and consequent immunosuppression. Nevertheless, the discovery of neurotransmitter receptors on immune cells, cytokine receptors on peripheral afferent nerve endings [2]–[5], and neural elements within immune organs has established the foundation for a more direct and reciprocal communication between the two systems. A deeper understanding of this interplay may provide new therapeutic tools for managing a wide range of immune-mediated disorders.

This review initially presents a detailed analysis of the pathophysiology of multiple sclerosis (MS) and the key immune cells and cytokines involved, in order to facilitate comprehension of the modulatory effects that neurotransmitters and their receptor agonists exert on specific immune cell populations and on disease processes in MS and its experimental model, experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE). It then focuses on the neural connections between the central nervous system and peripheral immune organs as a foundational step toward exploring their interaction. Subsequently, it reviews data regarding the expression of norepinephrine and acetylcholine receptors—two of the principal neurotransmitters of the nervous system—on immune cells and discusses the effects these molecules exert on immune function under various physiological and pathological conditions. Finally, it summarizes research findings on how these neurotransmitters or receptor agonists influence the clinical course and progression of EAE and multiple sclerosis.

Pathophysiology of Multiple Sclerosis and Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory, demyelinating, and neurodegenerative disease of the central nervous system (CNS), characterized by destructive lesions affecting myelin sheaths and the underlying axons. Although its precise etiology and pathogenic mechanisms remain incompletely elucidated—accounting for the currently symptomatic and often only partially effective therapeutic strategies—current evidence suggests that both genetic and environmental factors contribute to disease development.

Research indicates that the pathological process of MS is initiated by myelin-reactive CD4⁺ T lymphocytes of the Th1 and Th17 subtypes. These autoreactive cells penetrate the blood–brain barrier (BBB), become reactivated within the CNS, and release cytokines and chemokines that trigger an inflammatory cascade directed against myelin and axons. This inflammatory environment further activates cytotoxic CD8⁺ T cells, B cells, macrophages, and microglia, amplifying tissue injury.

The principal experimental model of MS is experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE), which is induced in mice by transferring CD4⁺ Th1 lymphocytes isolated from animals immunized with myelin antigens. The recipient mice subsequently develop demyelinating lesions in the CNS accompanied by neurological symptoms and histopathological findings that parallel the relapsing–remitting pattern observed in human MS [6].

The first pathognomonic T helper subset implicated in EAE pathogenesis was Th1. Th1 differentiation requires interleukin-12 (IL-12), the transcription factors STAT4 and T-box, and results in the production of interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α). Th1 cells play an essential role in defense against intracellular

pathogens. IL-12, a heterodimeric cytokine composed of p35 (IL12A) and p40 (IL12B) subunits, is secreted by antigen-presenting cells (APCs) and exerts pleiotropic effects on NK cells and both CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T lymphocytes. IL-12 activates the STAT4 pathway, leading to IFN- γ expression. When IFN- γ binds its receptor, it triggers JAK1/2–STAT1 signaling, inducing or repressing specific gene sets. IFN- γ enhances APC activity by upregulating MHC class II and costimulatory molecules (CD80, CD86). Elevated IFN- γ levels correlate with EAE severity, indicating a pathogenic role. However, paradoxically, anti-IFN- γ antibody therapy worsened disease, and IFN- γ -deficient mice exhibited more severe pathology, whereas administration of recombinant IFN- γ improved disease outcomes—suggesting a context-dependent, dual role of this cytokine.

Another major pro-inflammatory cytokine in MS and EAE is TNF- α , which is abundantly expressed in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and active lesions. TNF- α mediates cell death cascades through the activation of classical pathways such as nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), and caspase-dependent apoptosis. Importantly, the p40 subunit of IL-12 is also shared by IL-23, a cytokine composed of p19 and p40 subunits. Studies have demonstrated that mice deficient in IL-23p19 or IL-12p40 are resistant to EAE, whereas IL-12p35 deficiency does not confer protection—indicating that IL-23, not IL-12, is indispensable for disease induction, and that Th1 cells are not the sole pathogenic subset [6].

A newer subset, Th17 cells, has been shown to play a pivotal role. Th17 cells provide protection against bacterial and fungal infections mediated by TLR2 signaling but are also critical mediators of autoimmunity, including rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease, systemic lupus erythematosus, and MS. Their importance in EAE was underscored by the resistance of IL-23p19 knockout mice to disease induction, in contrast to IL-12p35 knockouts. IL-23, secreted by APCs, drives Th17 differentiation from naïve CD4⁺ cells during antigen presentation. Moreover, adoptive transfer of myelin-specific Th17 cells is sufficient to induce EAE in naïve mice. Th17 differentiation is promoted by IL-23, IL-1 β , IL-6, and transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), under the control of transcription factors ROR γ t and STAT3, and is maintained by IL-23 signaling. Th17 cells express the chemokine receptor CCR6, whose interaction with its ligand CCL20 is critical for CNS entry. These cells produce IL-17, IL-21, IL-22, IL-23, and granulocyte–macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF), a cytokine indispensable for EAE induction since GM-CSF-deficient mice are resistant to disease. IL-1 β , produced by activated macrophages, is another key cytokine promoting cell proliferation and apoptosis. In IL-1 β knockout mice, EAE manifests in significantly attenuated form. IL-1 β contributes to Th17 differentiation, T-cell recruitment, and CNS tissue damage, while also increasing BBB permeability to facilitate immune cell infiltration. Recent evidence suggests that IL-1 β -dependent crosstalk between endothelial cells, neutrophils, and monocytes drives early neuroinflammation in EAE. Additionally, IL-33, a member of the IL-1 cytokine family, has been found elevated in the spinal cords of EAE mice, indicating a possible pathogenic role [6].

Numerous studies have demonstrated the disease-modifying effects of interferon-beta (IFN- β) in MS. IFN- β , a type I interferon produced in response to viral or neoplastic stimuli, exerts potent anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects. Clinically, IFN- β has long been used in relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS), with approximately 80% of treated patients experiencing prolonged

remission and reduced relapse frequency and severity. This therapeutic efficacy parallels its capacity to suppress EAE, supporting its immunoregulatory function [6].

Regulatory T cells (Tregs) also play a crucial role in MS pathogenesis. They arise either naturally in the thymus or are induced peripherally, and their maintenance is supported by TGF- β during antigen presentation. Tregs suppress Th1 and Th17 responses via secretion of IL-10 and TGF- β . Dysfunctional Tregs can lead to exaggerated inflammation, tissue damage, and sustained autoimmunity. IL-10, a potent anti-inflammatory cytokine, inhibits pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, adhesion molecules, and antigen presentation. Administration of IL-10 prevents and ameliorates EAE but carries a theoretical risk of oncogenesis due to its suppressive effects on immune surveillance [6].

Another cytokine of interest is IL-6, which exerts both peripheral pro-inflammatory and CNS neuroprotective effects. It stimulates astrocytes to produce neurotrophic factors and nerve growth factor (NGF), supporting neuronal and oligodendrocyte survival near inactive MS plaques. IL-6 also enhances oligodendrocyte precursor cell differentiation and protects neurons from glutamate excitotoxicity via adenosine A1 receptor upregulation. Similarly, IL-1 β activates astrocytes to restore BBB integrity after CNS injury while inducing the production of NGF and ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF), both of which promote repair and cellular survival [6].

Innervation of Immune Organs

Studies by Nance and Hopkins (1987) and later by Trotter (2006) in mice demonstrated that thymic innervation derives exclusively from the sympathetic nervous system [8], [9]. Similarly, the spleen receives solely sympathetic input from prevertebral sympathetic ganglia, with no evidence of parasympathetic innervation [10], [11], [12].

Multiple earlier investigations—most notably those conducted by Felten and colleagues—identified sympathetic noradrenergic nerve fibers within lymph nodes and gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) across various mammalian species. This innervation is not random but rather regionally organized, predominantly localizing within T-cell-rich zones of lymphoid organs [13].

In contrast to the thymus and spleen, neuroanatomical evidence indicates the presence of afferent sensory nerve fibers in the lymph nodes of guinea pigs [14], suggesting a possible regulatory role during local inflammatory responses in the skin through the release of neuropeptides with pro-inflammatory activity. This neural activation occurs following exposure to pathogenic or damaging stimuli—such as microbial invasion or chemical injury—and may lead to the activation of regional draining lymph nodes, thereby mobilizing immune cells to counteract the underlying threat to the organism [15].

To date, parasympathetic innervation of lymph nodes has not been demonstrated in any experimental study [16]. Functional and histological analyses have also revealed that the bone marrow is innervated exclusively by the sympathetic nervous system, with no corresponding parasympathetic input [13].

Collectively, these findings establish that primary and secondary lymphoid organs are under substantial sympathetic control. Through this network, neurotransmitters such as norepinephrine can directly influence the development, mobilization, and

activation of immune cells, thus providing a neuroanatomical substrate for the bidirectional communication between the nervous and immune systems.

Expression of Adrenergic Receptors on Immune Cells

Adrenergic receptors (ARs) utilize adrenaline and noradrenaline as their principal ligands. They belong to the family of seven-transmembrane G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) and are categorized into three main types— α_1 , α_2 , and β —each of which comprises several subtypes expressed in both the central nervous system (CNS) and peripheral tissues [17].

Neutrophils

Using RT-qPCR, Nicholls et al. (2017) demonstrated mRNA expression of multiple adrenergic receptor subtypes in human neutrophils, including α_1A , α_1B , α_1D , α_2A , α_2B , α_2C , β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 , with β_2 -adrenergic receptor (β_2 -AR) mRNA showing the highest expression levels [18]. Earlier studies by Pohl and Urbanek confirmed the presence of β_2 -ARs on the surface of neutrophils isolated from both healthy children and those with atopic dermatitis, further supporting functional adrenergic responsiveness in these cells [19].

Monocytes and Macrophages

Binding assays and flow cytometry analyses have shown that human monocytes express β_2 -adrenergic receptors [20], [21]. Later RT-PCR studies revealed transcription of several α_1 -adrenergic receptor subtypes (α_1A , α_1B , α_1D) in monocytes derived from primary (bone marrow, spleen) and secondary (tonsils) lymphoid tissues, though not in monocytes isolated from peripheral blood. These findings suggest tissue-dependent heterogeneity in adrenergic receptor expression among monocyte populations [22].

Dendritic Cells

Maestroni (2000) reported that immature murine dendritic cells express α_1B -adrenergic receptor mRNA, which is downregulated during their maturation in lymph nodes [23]. Subsequent studies detected mRNA expression of α_1A , β_1 , and β_2 receptors in Langerhans cells and other dendritic cell subsets [24]. Additional data confirmed the presence of β_1 , β_2 , α_2A , and α_2C receptor transcripts in bone marrow-derived dendritic cells, indicating a broad adrenergic receptor repertoire that may modulate their maturation and cytokine production [25].

T and B Lymphocytes

According to Sanders (2006), both murine and human $CD4^+$ and $CD8^+$ T lymphocytes express β_2 -adrenergic receptors, with higher expression levels in $CD8^+$ cells [26]. Earlier ligand-binding studies (Sanders, 1997) demonstrated detectable β_2 -ARs on Th1 cells but not on Th2 cells [27], a difference later attributed to epigenetic silencing of β_2 -AR gene expression in Th2 subsets [28]. Subsequent work identified mRNA for β_1 , β_2 , and α_2A receptors in naïve $CD4^+$ T cells and $CD4^+Foxp3^+$ regulatory T cells [29].

Similarly, B lymphocytes have been shown to express β_2 -adrenergic receptors, as evidenced by radioligand binding and immunofluorescence studies in murine models [30]. Some studies also suggest the presence of α -adrenergic receptor subtypes, though their functional role remains less well characterized [31].

Microglia

Adrenergic receptor expression has not yet been characterized in human microglial cells. However, studies in murine models using microarray and immunohistochemical approaches have confirmed the presence of β_1 -, β_2 -, and α_2 -adrenergic receptors on microglial cell surfaces, implicating sympathetic neurotransmitters in microglial activation and neuroimmune signaling [32].

Astrocytes

Astrocytes have been shown to express exclusively β_2 -adrenergic receptors, as highlighted in the review by Scanzano and Cosentino (2015) [33]. Activation of these receptors modulates astrocytic cytokine production, metabolic support to neurons, and neuroprotective functions within the CNS.

Norepinephrine and Immune Cells

The principal site of norepinephrine production in the brain is the locus coeruleus, located on the dorsal aspect of the pons, along the floor of the fourth ventricle. This nucleus gives rise to ascending and descending noradrenergic fibers that innervate numerous regions of the central nervous system, including the forebrain, cerebellum, brainstem, and spinal cord. Within the forebrain, the noradrenergic projections of the locus coeruleus target regions particularly vulnerable to neurodegeneration in Alzheimer's disease, such as the hippocampus, frontal cortex, and entorhinal cortex [34].

Neutrophils

As described earlier, evidence supports the presence of adrenergic receptors on neutrophils, with β_2 -adrenergic receptors (β_2 -ARs) being the predominant subtype. Experimental studies have shown that administration of the β_2 -selective agonist *isoproterenol* inhibits the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by human neutrophils, thereby reducing tissue-damaging oxidative stress [35]. Similarly, treatment of IL-1–stimulated human endothelial cells and neutrophils with adrenaline or norepinephrine significantly suppressed neutrophil adhesion to activated endothelium [36].

Further investigations demonstrated that norepinephrine, adrenaline, and isoproterenol exert minimal effects on resting neutrophils but, upon activation, decrease their migratory capacity, reduce adhesion molecule expression, and suppress ROS generation. These effects are primarily mediated through β_2 -AR stimulation, though α -adrenergic receptor involvement cannot be completely excluded [37]. Moreover, exposure of activated neutrophils to isoproterenol inhibited the formation of neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs)—a key antimicrobial defense mechanism—suggesting a suppressive effect of β_2 -AR activation on neutrophil effector functions [38].

Animal studies corroborate these findings. In a murine model of experimental colitis, chronic stress led to increased neutrophil infiltration into colonic tissue, accompanied by elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-17A, IL-22) and neutrophil-attracting chemokines (CXCL1, CXCL2), as well as hyperactivation of the STAT3 inflammatory signaling pathway. These effects were mediated through β -adrenergic receptor activation resulting from stress-induced catecholamine elevation

and could be reproduced by isoproterenol administration or reversed by the β -blocker propranolol [39].

Similarly, chronic stress and catecholamine surges were shown to increase the recruitment of polymorphonuclear neutrophils to skin wounds in mice, delaying tissue repair by sustaining local inflammation [40]. These findings align with clinical observations that chronic stress often precipitates relapses or exacerbations of autoimmune diseases.

Conversely, acute catecholaminergic stimulation appears to suppress neutrophil chemotaxis and activation. Norepinephrine treatment of murine neutrophils inhibited their migration toward chemoattractants and reduced phagocytic activity both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. In a model of ischemic stroke—characterized by elevated sympathetic outflow—neutrophils isolated from affected mice exhibited diminished chemotactic responsiveness, supporting the concept that acute adrenergic activation dampens neutrophil mobilization [18].

Consistent with these findings, β_2 -adrenergic agonists such as isoproterenol have been shown to reduce neutrophil infiltration and pro-inflammatory cytokine production in murine models of peritonitis in a dose-dependent manner [41]. Moreover, depletion of peripheral catecholamines using *reserpine* abolished the LPS-induced increase in circulating neutrophils, an effect that could be reproduced by α_1 -adrenergic antagonists [42]. This suggests that sympathetic innervation of lymphoid organs may regulate neutrophil mobilization during infection.

In summary, catecholamines exert a complex regulatory influence on neutrophil activity—primarily immunosuppressive following inflammatory activation, yet potentially pro-inflammatory under conditions of chronic stress. The precise mechanisms and context-dependent effects of adrenergic modulation on neutrophils warrant further investigation to clarify their therapeutic potential in immune-mediated diseases.

Monocytes and Macrophages

Monocytes and macrophages are among the principal antigen-presenting cells of the immune system and are also major producers of cytokines. In addition, macrophages retain strong phagocytic capacity, enabling them to engulf pathogens and cellular debris. As noted earlier, these cells express β -adrenergic receptors, whose activation by catecholamines or selective agonists elicits diverse immunomodulatory effects depending on the microenvironment and activation state.

In one of the earliest studies on the topic, Schopf and Lemmel (1983) demonstrated that incubation of antigen-stimulated polymorphonuclear and mononuclear cells with the β_2 -adrenergic agonist *fenoterol* led to a dose-dependent reduction in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) *in vitro* [43]. Subsequent research confirmed that treatment of peripheral blood monocytes with *isoproterenol* diminished their phagocytic capacity against *Candida albicans* [44]. Furthermore, β_2 -adrenergic stimulation of human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) activated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS) resulted in decreased production of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-18 and IL-12 *in vitro* [45].

In contrast, Swanson and colleagues observed that exposure of antigen-presenting cells to norepinephrine during peptide antigen presentation to immature T cells did not alter IL-12 secretion [46]. The discrepancy between these studies likely reflects

differences in the activation pathways of APCs: while LPS activates innate immune signaling via pattern-recognition receptors, peptide antigens trigger the MHC class II-mediated adaptive immune response. Collectively, these findings suggest that norepinephrine acts as a negative regulator of excessive innate immune activation—serving as a safeguard against cytokine storm—while in lymphoid microenvironments it may enhance the development of adaptive immunity.

Additional studies reported that exposure of LPS-activated PBMCs to adrenaline or isoproterenol led to a dose-dependent reduction in macrophage inflammatory protein-1 α (MIP-1 α) production, a chemokine essential for leukocyte recruitment and the propagation of inflammation [47]. Similarly, β_2 -adrenergic stimulation of monocyte-derived human macrophages activated by LPS decreased the production of several pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, including TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, CCL2, CCL3, and CCL4. Interestingly, this effect was absent in pulmonary macrophages, which were found to lack β_2 -receptor expression [48], consistent with reports showing that β -receptor functionality diminishes as monocytes differentiate into macrophages *in vitro* [49].

Norepinephrine administration in LPS-activated murine macrophage cultures enhanced phagocytic activity while reducing markers of the M1 pro-inflammatory phenotype and promoting an M2 anti-inflammatory profile [50]. Likewise, treatment with the β_2 -agonist *salbutamol* inhibited activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome—a pro-inflammatory multiprotein complex—and reduced TNF- α and IL-1 β production both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [51]. Similar immunosuppressive effects were observed when norepinephrine was applied to LPS-stimulated splenic macrophages from rats, leading to decreased TNF secretion [52].

In related experiments, *salbutamol* administration suppressed TNF- α and IL-6 production and inhibited *iNOS* mRNA transcription in LPS-stimulated macrophages [53]. In mouse splenocyte cultures exposed to LPS, adrenaline markedly reduced TNF- α and IL-6 levels while enhancing IL-10 production, further confirming a shift toward an anti-inflammatory profile [54]. Additionally, β_2 -receptor activation in LPS-activated murine macrophages inhibited the release of IL-27—a cytokine known to promote Th1 differentiation [55].

Parallel studies in human monocytes showed that norepinephrine and isoproterenol decreased the LPS-induced expression of CD14, ICAM-1, and CD40 molecules in a dose-dependent manner, as well as TNF- α production [56] and T-cell proliferation, redirecting the T-cell response from a Th1 toward a Th2 phenotype [57]. β_2 -adrenergic stimulation in both human monocytes and CD40-activated dendritic cells consistently suppressed IL-12 production [58], while combined treatment with norepinephrine and adrenaline in LPS-stimulated whole blood reduced IL-12 but increased IL-10 in a dose-dependent fashion [59].

Moreover, administration of β_2 -agonists to LPS-stimulated human monocytes induced upregulation of IL-8 (CXCL8), a chemokine that attracts neutrophils, along with enhanced IL-10 production [60]—again demonstrating dual immunomodulatory capacity. The β_2 -agonist *clenbuterol* further inhibited the differentiation of monocytes into dendritic cells, decreased TNF- α production, and enhanced IL-6 and IL-10 secretion [61]. Similar inhibitory effects on TNF- α and IL-8 were confirmed in THP-1 monocyte cultures stimulated with LPS, mediated via β_2 -adrenergic receptor activation [62], [63].

Interestingly, stimulation of bone marrow–derived murine monocytes with isoproterenol or catecholamines increased CD14 expression—enhancing their sensitivity to LPS—and augmented phagocytic capacity [64]. Catecholamine exposure also elevated macrophage phagocytosis while reducing MHC class II and CCR2 expression, proliferation, and chemotaxis toward MCP-1, indicating a coordinated shift toward resolution of inflammation [65], [66]. In porcine macrophages, β_2 -adrenergic stimulation suppressed LPS-induced TNF- α and IL-8 secretion and increased IL-10 production, collectively preventing polarization toward a pro-inflammatory M1 phenotype [67].

Taken together, the available evidence indicates that catecholamines exert predominantly immunosuppressive effects on monocytes and macrophages. However, under specific experimental conditions—depending on catecholamine concentration, exposure duration, cell origin, and activation state—they may also exhibit pro-inflammatory activity. Elucidating these context-dependent mechanisms is essential for harnessing the immunomodulatory potential of catecholaminergic signaling, particularly given the widespread clinical use of β -blockers and β -agonists, whose effects on patients' immune profiles remain incompletely understood.

Dendritic Cells

Dendritic cells (DCs) constitute the most potent antigen-presenting cells of the immune system and serve as an essential bridge between innate and adaptive immunity. They internalize antigens through phagocytosis, process them into peptides, and present them on MHC class II molecules to naïve T lymphocytes, thereby initiating antigen-specific immune responses [1].

Maestroni (2000) demonstrated that immature bone marrow–derived dendritic cells express α_1 B-adrenergic receptors, which are downregulated as the cells mature within lymphoid tissues. Subsequent studies identified β_2 -adrenergic receptor expression in multiple DC subsets and confirmed that norepinephrine modulates their functional maturation and cytokine secretion profiles.

More specifically, the administration of norepinephrine to a mixed population of dendritic cells isolated from human umbilical cord blood resulted in suppression of LPS-induced production of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-23, IL-12p40, TNF- α , and IL-6. The data indicated that this effect was mediated through β -adrenergic receptor activation [68].

Comparable results were obtained in another study, in which salmeterol administration to LPS- and peptide antigen–stimulated murine dendritic cell cultures reduced the production of the pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, whereas in an *in vivo* mouse model of asthma, the same β_2 -agonist attenuated inflammation of the pulmonary parenchyma [69].

Similarly, treatment of human monocyte cultures stimulated with IFN- γ and LPS with the β_2 -adrenergic agonist salbutamol led to decreased IL-12 production [58]. An identical outcome was observed in human dendritic cells stimulated via CD40, in which salbutamol exposure suppressed IL-12 secretion [58].

In one study, the administration of norepinephrine to immature dendritic cells isolated from murine bone marrow enhanced their migratory capacity from peripheral tissues to regional lymph nodes via activation of α_1 B-adrenergic receptors. This effect was

not observed in mature CD40-stimulated dendritic cells, which were found to no longer express this receptor subtype [23].

Another investigation reported that brief exposure of murine dendritic cells to norepinephrine at the time of LPS stimulation resulted in reduced IL-12 production and increased IL-10 secretion through activation of β - and α_2 -adrenergic receptors. This shift was accompanied by an impaired ability of these cells to induce Th1 immune responses [70].

Similarly, *in vitro* administration of norepinephrine to LPS-stimulated murine dendritic cells led to a significant decrease in IL-12p70 production—an essential cytokine for Th1 polarization—without affecting IL-23 synthesis, a cytokine that promotes Th17 differentiation. Consequently, norepinephrine treatment increased the IL-12p70/IL-23 ratio, suggesting selective suppression of Th1-promoting cytokine pathways [71].

In another study, administration of epinephrine to murine bone marrow-derived dendritic cells enhanced their endocytic capacity via activation of α -adrenergic receptors. Pretreatment of these cell cultures with epinephrine or the β_2 -adrenergic agonist salbutamol, followed by stimulation with LPS, resulted in increased IL-10 production and marked suppression of IL-12p70 and IL-23 levels. Subsequent antigenic stimulation of these dendritic cells with ovalbumin and co-culture with CD4⁺ T helper lymphocytes, after prior exposure to epinephrine or salbutamol, induced a pronounced Th2 immune response and promoted the differentiation of Foxp3⁺ regulatory T cells [72].

In line with these findings, another experimental study demonstrated that concurrent exposure of murine dendritic cells to norepinephrine and LPS *in vitro* led to a dramatic increase in IL-33 mRNA expression—an interleukin strongly associated with Th2 polarization. Moreover, under experimental conditions involving apoptotic cell presence, the same combination of norepinephrine and LPS exposure enhanced IL-33 protein production and release through β_2 -adrenergic receptor-mediated mechanisms [73].

Adopting a different experimental approach, one study demonstrated that stimulation of murine dendritic cells with specific ligands for the intracellular pattern-recognition receptors NOD2 and TLR2, followed by β_2 -adrenergic agonist (salbutamol) exposure, resulted in a marked increase in IL-6 and IL-23 production, whereas salbutamol addition suppressed IL-12 synthesis. These findings indicate a shift toward Th17 immune polarization at the expense of Th1 responses. The same study confirmed this Th17-skewing effect *in vivo* in an experimental mouse model [74].

In another investigation, epinephrine administration to murine bone marrow-derived dendritic cells, followed by LPS stimulation, enhanced the expression of MHC class II and the costimulatory molecules CD80 and CD86. At the same time, IL-12p40 and IL-12p70 levels decreased, while IL-12p35, IL-10, and IL-23p19 expression increased. These combined effects translated into suppression of Th1 priming and promotion of a dominant Th2/Th17 profile [75].

Subsequently, it was shown that treatment of epidermal dendritic cells (Langerhans cells) with epinephrine or norepinephrine inhibited their antigen-presenting capacity through β_2 -adrenergic receptor signaling [24]. Consistent with this, a later study demonstrated that exposure of murine LPS- and peptide antigen-stimulated dendritic cells to the β_2 -agonist salbutamol reduced their antigen-presenting ability by

interfering with the intracellular antigen degradation pathway. This effect was confirmed *in vivo* in the same study [76].

A subsequent report further revealed that, during co-culture of CD4⁺ T cells with murine dendritic cells stimulated by LPS and peptide antigen, salbutamol administration inhibited proliferation of peptide-specific CD4⁺ T lymphocytes and reduced secretion of the pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-6, while maintaining IL-10 production [77]. In contrast, another study showed that exposure of murine dendritic cells to a selective α_2 -adrenergic agonist increased their endocytic capacity [78].

In a distinct immuno-oncologic context, research using a model of “cold” head and neck tumor revealed that administration of the β -blocker propranolol together with anti-CD40 (an agonistic antibody to the CD40 receptor) exerted a potent immunostimulatory effect, leading to marked tumor regression, enhanced cytotoxic T-cell infiltration, and reduced intratumoral regulatory T-cell presence compared to monotherapy. This synergistic effect was attributed to reversal of β_2 -adrenergic receptor-mediated suppression of endogenous CD40 function, which plays a critical role in maintaining dendritic cell immunocompetence [79].

Overall, these observations indicate that norepinephrine and β_2 -adrenergic receptor activation skew dendritic cells toward a tolerogenic, anti-inflammatory phenotype characterized by low IL-12 and TNF- α and high IL-10 production. This shift limits excessive Th1-driven inflammation but may also impair effective immune responses against pathogens. Understanding how adrenergic modulation shapes DC function could inform novel therapeutic strategies for autoimmune diseases, chronic inflammation, and neuroimmune regulation.

T Lymphocytes

T lymphocytes constitute a key cellular population of the adaptive immune system, giving rise to several subsets including helper (CD4⁺), cytotoxic (CD8⁺), and regulatory (Treg) T cells, each with distinct roles in the induction, execution, and resolution of specific immune responses. These cells, as previously mentioned, express adrenergic receptors on their surface, activation of which leads to modulation of their immune functions [1].

Early observations showed that antigen exposure induces, within 24 hours, an increase in norepinephrine release from peripheral sympathetic nerve endings in primary and secondary lymphoid organs located near immature CD4⁺ T cells [80–82]. Thus, norepinephrine becomes biochemically available in the immediate microenvironment of naïve CD4⁺ T cells during the critical window of T-cell activation and differentiation [83].

In vivo studies in mice demonstrated that administration of β_2 -adrenergic agonists reduced lymphocyte egress from lymph nodes into the circulation via effects on the chemokine receptors CCR7 and CXCR4, thereby promoting lymphocyte retention within lymphoid tissues [84]. Consistent with these findings, RT-PCR and pharmacological assays employing selective adrenergic agonists showed that immature CD4⁺ T cells express β_2 -adrenergic receptors, and that norepinephrine binding to these receptors promotes differentiation toward a Th1 phenotype characterized by enhanced IFN- γ production. Increased IFN- γ synthesis resulted from reactivation of existing IFN- γ -producing cells rather than proliferation of new

ones. However, this norepinephrine-driven Th1 polarization was observed only in the presence of IL-12 in the culture medium, suggesting a permissive rather than primary role of norepinephrine in Th1 induction [46].

Similarly, genetically modified mice unable to synthesize norepinephrine exhibited increased susceptibility to Th1-inducing pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, accompanied by impaired IFN- γ production and T-cell dysfunction [85].

Conversely, other studies indicate that catecholaminergic signaling can shift immunity toward Th2 responses. In neonatal CD4⁺ T-cell cultures stimulated with phytohemagglutinin (PHA)—a potent mitogen that strongly induces IFN- γ — β_2 -adrenergic agonist treatment suppressed Th1 differentiation and enhanced Th2 responses [58]. Likewise, exposure of Th1-differentiated murine T cells to the β_2 -agonist terbutaline prior to activation by antigen-presenting B cells reduced IFN- γ secretion and diminished IgG2 α production by B cells. By contrast, similar exposure of Th2 cells produced no functional changes, and radioligand binding assays confirmed the absence of β_2 -adrenergic receptors on Th2 cells [27,28].

Norepinephrine administration to cultures of naïve CD4⁺ T cells activated independently of antigen-presenting cells decreased IL-2 production—a cytokine critical for T-cell proliferation and survival during differentiation [29,86].

Of particular interest, *in vivo* administration of norepinephrine in mice reduced pro-inflammatory cytokine production by splenic cells through actions on atypical suppressor T lymphocytes (CD3⁺CD4⁺CD25⁻) [87]. Similarly, norepinephrine treatment in co-cultures of Treg cells with naïve T cells enhanced the suppressive capacity of the Tregs and decreased proliferation of the responder population, while also promoting the differentiation of naïve T cells into suppressive phenotypes [29]. Moreover, β_2 -adrenergic agonist (terbutaline) co-stimulation of splenic CD4⁺ T cells activated with anti-CD3/anti-CD28 resulted in a dose-dependent reduction in IL-2 and IFN- γ production and inhibition of T-cell proliferation [88].

From a translational standpoint, *in vivo* β_2 -blockade in murine tumor vaccination models enhanced infiltration of cytotoxic CD8⁺ T cells into the tumor microenvironment, leading to increased tumor regression. This effect likely stemmed from inhibition of catecholamine-mediated suppression of effector T-cell differentiation within tumor-draining lymph nodes [89]. In agreement, reduction of β -adrenergic signaling—either through genetic deletion of β_2 receptors or pharmacologic β -blockade—in experimental mouse cancer models augmented antitumor immunity, characterized by increased intratumoral CD8⁺ T-cell infiltration and a higher CD8⁺/Treg ratio, indicating reversal of immunosuppressive adrenergic effects [90].

In addition, propranolol administration to cultures of neuroantigen-specific T cells from draining lymph nodes of mice increased IL-1 β and IL-23/p19 expression, along with expansion of IL-17⁺ CD4⁺ T cells, suggesting that catecholamines may exert suppressive effects on mature, neuroantigen-reactive CD4⁺ T-cell responses [91].

B Lymphocytes

Regarding B-cell function, an *in vivo* mouse study demonstrated that chemical depletion of peripheral norepinephrine impaired antibody production by antigen-stimulated B lymphocytes. This finding highlights the potential underlying importance

of catecholaminergic stimulation in facilitating T–B cell interactions required for effective humoral immunity. Moreover, norepinephrine deficiency inhibited the formation of germinal centers in peripheral lymphoid organs [30].

Similarly, mice subjected to peripheral norepinephrine depletion exhibited reduced expression of the costimulatory molecule B7-2 (CD86) on B lymphocytes following activation of their B-cell receptor (BCR) by antigen, suggesting an auxiliary role for norepinephrine in promoting antibody-mediated immune responses [92].

Microglial Cells

Microglial cells represent a resident population of immune cells within the central nervous system (CNS), endowed with multiple roles including the development and maintenance of neuronal networks, surveillance of the CNS microenvironment for potential pathogen invasion, initiation of inflammatory responses, clearance of cellular debris resulting from such inflammation, and promotion of neurogenesis and neuroplasticity. Thus, microglia participate in both destructive and regenerative processes affecting CNS cell populations and structures, depending on the prevailing conditions [93]. Numerous studies have also demonstrated the involvement of catecholamines in these mechanisms.

Pro-inflammatory Role of Norepinephrine in Microglia

A significant body of evidence indicates that microglia respond to various stressors—including acute stress, repeated stress, and social defeat stress—conditions known to activate both the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis and the sympathetic nervous system (SNS). The resulting elevations of glucocorticoids and catecholamines vary depending on the type and intensity of stress [94].

In this context, one study demonstrated that physical stress exposure in mice activates noradrenergic neurons within the CNS, leading to increased catecholaminergic activity both centrally and peripherally. This effect could be mitigated by prior regular physical exercise, which rendered the noradrenergic system less responsive to stress stimuli [95].

Concomitantly, stress exposure was shown to increase IL-1 β production within the CNS, while administration of the β -adrenergic agonist isoproterenol in the absence of stress or infection similarly elevated IL-1 β levels in the brain and both IL-1 β and IL-6 levels in plasma. Of particular interest, lesioning of the locus coeruleus—the principal source of norepinephrine in the CNS through its extensive efferent projections—abolished stress-induced IL-1 β elevation in brain regions densely innervated by this system [96].

Complementary findings revealed that in models of acute, chronic, and social defeat stress—each characterized by activation of the HPA axis and SNS—microglial activation and production of pro-inflammatory cytokines were suppressed by β -adrenergic blockade with propranolol [97–99]. These data further support the notion that sympathetic hyperactivity under stress promotes pro-inflammatory microglial activation via catecholamine signaling through β -adrenergic receptors expressed on microglia.

Moreover, in cultured murine microglial cells, exposure to the β -adrenergic agonist isoproterenol increased IL-1 β mRNA expression [100]. A similar effect was observed

with norepinephrine treatment [101] and under *in vivo* conditions in subsequent studies [102]. In microglial cultures, isoproterenol administration also upregulated mRNA and protein levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-6. In the same study, β -blockers inhibited postoperative stress-induced microglial activation in mice [99].

Further evidence from acute stress models confirmed that β -blocker pretreatment prevented stress-induced pro-inflammatory microglial activation in the brain. Likewise, genetically modified mice lacking β_1 and β_2 -adrenergic receptor genes displayed markedly reduced microglial activation compared to wild-type controls [103]. Consistent with this, propranolol therapy has been shown to decrease microglial activity and cerebral inflammation in multiple models of neurological disease [104–107].

Finally, experimental data indicate that administration of the β_2 -adrenergic agonist salmeterol to murine microglial–dopaminergic neuron co-cultures induced pro-inflammatory microglial activation and reactive oxygen species generation, ultimately triggering neuronal death [108].

Anti-inflammatory Role of Norepinephrine in Microglia

A substantial body of research, however, highlights the anti-inflammatory effects of norepinephrine on microglial cells. Specifically, in cultures of murine microglia stimulated with LPS, administration of norepinephrine, terbutaline (a β_2 -adrenergic agonist), and phenylephrine (an α_1 -adrenergic agonist) reduced nitric oxide production, a mediator with pro-inflammatory properties. Furthermore, in co-cultures of murine microglia and neurons exposed to LPS, treatment with these agents increased neuronal survival despite the presence of the bacterial endotoxin, while reducing mRNA expression of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and IL-6, as well as inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS). These effects were attributed to β_2 - and α_1 -receptor–mediated suppression of NF- κ B nuclear translocation and subsequent inhibition of STAT1 phosphorylation [109].

Consistent findings across multiple studies indicate that activation of β -adrenergic receptors in murine microglial cultures suppresses LPS-induced production of IL-6, TNF- α , IL-12, and nitric oxide—all of which possess pro-inflammatory activity [110–113]. Stimulation of β -adrenergic receptors has also been shown to inhibit LPS-induced TNF- α release from microglia [114], while in guinea pig microglial cultures, pretreatment with the β -agonist isoproterenol suppressed the generation of reactive oxygen species [115].

Similarly, norepinephrine administration in murine microglial cultures inhibited IFN- γ –induced MHC class II expression on the cell surface [116]. Norepinephrine also suppressed the expression of NOS2 and IL-1 β in LPS-stimulated microglia via β_2 -adrenergic receptor signaling [117]. In comparable experimental setups, norepinephrine, phenylephrine (α_1 -agonist), dobutamine (β_1 -agonist), and terbutaline (β_2 -agonist) reduced mRNA expression of IL-6 and TNF- α , as well as the secretion of TNF- α and nitric oxide [118].

Further *in vivo* evidence supports these findings. Selective ablation of the locus coeruleus and norepinephrine system in mice, followed by systemic LPS administration, resulted in exacerbation of systemic and neuroinflammatory responses, with increased production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and activation of

microglia and astrocytes, particularly in the hippocampus [119]. Similarly, treatment of mice with the noradrenergic neurotoxin DSP4, which markedly reduced norepinephrine synthesis in locus coeruleus neurons, followed by administration of MPTP (1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine)—a dopaminergic neurotoxin—or LPS, led to altered microglial function characterized by prolonged pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, diminished neurotrophic factor production, and decreased antioxidant capacity in the substantia nigra, resulting in aggravated dopaminergic neurodegeneration. Collectively, these findings suggest a suppressive role for norepinephrine in pro-inflammatory microglial activation and thus a potentially neuroprotective function [120].

In line with this, hippocampal slice experiments in mice exposed to LPS and adrenergic α - or β -agonists under oxygen-glucose deprivation revealed that β_1 - and β_2 -adrenergic receptor activation on microglia conferred protection against neuronal death. This neuroprotection was attributed to reduced production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6, and MCP-1) and a phenotypic shift of microglia toward a neuroprotective profile [121].

Further evidence demonstrated that norepinephrine treatment of mixed glial cultures (microglia and astrocytes) induced the expression of the interleukin-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1ra) and the decoy receptor IL-1RI, both of which inhibit IL-1 β signaling in the CNS, suggesting that norepinephrine promotes anti-inflammatory regulatory pathways within glial populations [122]. Likewise, norepinephrine exposure in murine brain slices induced retraction of amoeboid processes in both resting and LPS-activated microglia via β_2 - and α_2A -adrenergic receptor signaling, respectively, thereby promoting an anti-inflammatory phenotype [123].

Finally, exposure of cortical neurons to conditioned medium from LPS-stimulated microglial cultures treated with norepinephrine prevented neuronal death that otherwise occurred in the absence of catecholaminergic signaling, likely due to norepinephrine-mediated suppression of IL-1 β production—a cytokine known for its neurotoxic role [124,125]. Similarly, isoproterenol exhibited neuroprotective effects in co-cultures of neurons and embryonic brain macrophages, attenuating microglia-induced neuronal death *in vitro* [126].

Overall, catecholaminergic stimulation exerts both pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory effects on microglia, raising questions about the conditions determining these divergent outcomes. A common denominator among studies reporting pro-inflammatory β -adrenergic effects is the absence of prior LPS activation before exposure to β -agonists or norepinephrine. In contrast, studies demonstrating immunosuppressive actions typically involve pre-existing microbial or inflammatory activation. Therefore, catecholaminergic stimulation during chronic stress likely promotes pro-inflammatory microglial activation, whereas under infectious or inflammatory conditions, it appears to exert predominantly anti-inflammatory influences.

Astrocytes

Another major cellular population of the CNS with a supportive role in maintaining neuronal function is represented by astrocytes. These glial cells regulate extracellular ion concentrations and glutamate homeostasis, provide defense against oxidative stress, contribute to scar formation following injury or extensive necrosis, and promote the repair and proper operation of neuronal synapses. In addition,

astrocytes are now recognized as active participants in immune processes [127]. As mentioned earlier, astrocytes express catecholamine receptors on their surface, rendering them potential targets for immunomodulatory effects mediated by these neurotransmitters.

Supporting this concept, several studies have demonstrated that norepinephrine modulates astrocytic immune functions. In murine astrocyte cultures, norepinephrine inhibited IFN- γ -induced upregulation of MHC class II molecules—key mediators of antigen presentation [128]. Likewise, norepinephrine suppressed induction of inducible nitric oxide synthase (NOS2), responsible for nitric oxide generation, in LPS-stimulated murine astrocytes [129]. In another study, norepinephrine promoted both mRNA and protein expression of IL-6 in neonatal murine astrocyte cultures via activation of α_1 - and β_2 -adrenergic receptors [130].

Through β -adrenergic receptor stimulation, norepinephrine also increased expression of the inhibitory molecule I κ B α in cortical astrocytes under LPS stimulation, thereby inactivating the transcription factor NF- κ B and preventing transcription of NF- κ B-dependent pro-inflammatory genes [131].

Additional studies further delineate norepinephrine's regulatory role in astrocytes. In LPS-stimulated murine astrocyte cultures, norepinephrine exposure inhibited production of the chemokine MCP-1 (monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 or CCL2), which normally recruits macrophages to sites of inflammation [132]. Another investigation showed that norepinephrine suppressed expression of adhesion molecules in murine astrocytes previously activated by IL-1 β and TNF- α [133].

Evidence suggesting a potentially immunosuppressive influence of norepinephrine on astrocytes comes from findings in multiple sclerosis, where astrocytes within demyelinating plaques and in normal-appearing white matter exhibit loss of β_2 -adrenergic receptors [134, 135].

Finally, norepinephrine was found to dose-dependently enhance glutamate uptake from the extracellular space in murine astrocyte cultures via α_1 -adrenergic receptor signaling, thereby protecting neurons from glutamate-mediated excitotoxicity [136]. Similarly, norepinephrine inhibited LPS-induced IL-1 β and TNF- α production in human astrocyte cell lines [137], while isoproterenol suppressed LPS-induced IL-6 and TNF- α release in murine astrocyte cultures [138].

Acetylcholine and Its Receptors in Immune Cells

Acetylcholine (ACh) is a neurotransmitter synthesized in the cytoplasm from choline and acetyl-coenzyme A (acetyl-CoA) in a single-step reaction catalyzed by the enzyme choline acetyltransferase (ChAT). ACh is rapidly hydrolyzed into choline and acetate by the enzymes acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE). It exerts its effects by binding to two distinct classes of receptors: the ionotropic nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) and the metabotropic muscarinic acetylcholine receptors (mAChRs).

A study employing RT-PCR demonstrated that thymic, splenic, and peripheral blood lymphocytes of mice express mRNA for choline acetyltransferase, indicating that these cells are capable of synthesizing acetylcholine endogenously. Furthermore, T lymphocytes were found to contain higher levels of acetylcholine than B lymphocytes. Stimulation of lymphoid cell lines with phytohemagglutinin (PHA) led to increased

ACh production and release, suggesting a functional role for acetylcholine in lymphocyte activation and signaling [139].

The first evidence of muscarinic and nicotinic cholinergic receptor expression on lymphocytes was reported in 1999. Using RT-PCR on human peripheral blood mononuclear cells and eight leukocyte cell lines, investigators identified mRNA transcripts encoding subunits of both nicotinic ($\alpha 2$ – $\alpha 7$ and $\beta 2$ – $\beta 4$) and muscarinic receptors (M1–M5), with distinct expression patterns depending on the cell line examined [140].

Muscarinic Receptors in Immune Cells

Muscarinic receptors are G-protein–coupled receptors classified into five subtypes (M1–M5). Among them, M2 and M4 subtypes exert inhibitory effects, whereas M1, M3, and M5 are excitatory [141]. These receptors are activated by muscarine, producing either inhibitory or stimulatory outcomes depending on the cell type in which they are expressed [142].

Subtypes M3, M4, and M5 have been identified in nearly all human peripheral blood lymphocytes, while the expression of M1 and M2 varies among individuals [140]. In a purified population of human T lymphocytes, mRNA for M3, M4, and M5 receptors was detected, whereas none of these subtypes were found in B lymphocytes or peripheral blood monocytes [143]. Another study identified mRNA transcripts for M1 and M2 receptors in peripheral blood lymphocytes, which were subsequently localized to CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T-cell subsets [144]. Later research provided evidence supporting the potential presence of M2–M5 receptors in B lymphocytes as well [145]. Finally, expression of mRNA corresponding to all five muscarinic receptor subtypes has been demonstrated in murine dendritic cells and macrophages [146].

Nicotinic Receptors in Immune Cells

Nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) can be classified into two major subtypes: (1) **α -bungarotoxin–sensitive receptors**, which are either homomeric or heteromeric assemblies composed of $\alpha 7$ – $\alpha 8$ and/or $\alpha 9$ – $\alpha 10$ subunits, and (2) **α -bungarotoxin–insensitive receptors**, which are heteromeric structures formed by combinations of α and β subunits and are activated by nicotine. The specific combination of subunits determines the receptor's structural configuration, conferring distinct biophysical and functional properties [147].

Initial studies demonstrated the presence of mRNA encoding the $\alpha 3$, $\alpha 5$, and $\beta 4$ subunits of nAChRs in human thymic cells. Subsequent work revealed that the expression profile of these subunits varies according to the stage of thymocyte maturation and their eventual functional phenotype (CD4⁺CD8⁺, CD4⁺CD8⁻, CD4⁻CD8⁺) [148–150]. Later research confirmed the existence of $\alpha 3$ and $\alpha 4$ subunits in human peripheral blood lymphocytes [151].

In a subsequent study, expression of the $\alpha 7$ nAChR subtype was identified in isolated human lymphocytes under both resting and activated conditions, and the receptor was shown to be functionally active [152]. Similarly, *in vitro* experiments revealed that $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression in non-stimulated human T lymphocytes increased eightfold following PHA stimulation, accompanied by a parallel rise in M5 muscarinic receptor expression [153]. Another study confirmed $\alpha 7$ nAChR protein expression on the surface of CD4⁺ T cells, which was upregulated during immune activation [154].

Furthermore, the $\alpha 4(\alpha 5)\beta 2$ and $\alpha 7(\alpha 5\beta 4)$ receptor subtypes have been identified in murine B lymphocytes, with their expression levels and relative abundance changing according to the stage of cellular maturation [155]. Later findings established $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression on human macrophages [156], while mRNA transcripts corresponding to nAChR subunits $\alpha 2$, $\alpha 5$, $\alpha 6$, $\alpha 7$, $\alpha 10$, and $\beta 2$ were detected in murine macrophages and dendritic cells [146]. The presence of $\alpha 7$ nAChRs has also been demonstrated on human monocytes and dendritic cells [157].

In addition, both murine primary microglial cultures and the N9 microglial cell line express $\alpha 7$ nAChR mRNA [158]. PCR analyses revealed that murine $CD4^+$ and $CD8^+$ T lymphocytes isolated from the spleen contain mRNA for $\alpha 5$, $\alpha 7$, $\alpha 9$, and $\beta 2$ nAChR subunits, while $CD8^+$ T cells also express $\alpha 4$ and $\beta 4$ subunits. $CD11b^+$ monocytes/macrophages express $\alpha 5$, $\alpha 7$, $\alpha 9$, $\beta 2$, and $\beta 4$ subunits, whereas dendritic cells additionally express $\alpha 4$. No nAChR transcripts could be detected in regulatory T cells. Murine microglia were shown to express a broad range of subunits, including $\alpha 3$, $\alpha 4$, $\alpha 5$, $\alpha 6$, $\alpha 7$, $\alpha 9$, $\beta 2$, $\beta 3$, and $\beta 4$ [159].

Acetylcholine and Immune Cells

Before describing the effects of acetylcholine on immune cells, it is important to introduce the concept of the *cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex* [160]. This mechanism, described about two decades ago, involves a reflex arc composed of the vagus nerve and immune cells within the spleen, ultimately leading to suppression of inflammatory activity [160].

Specifically, during activation of this reflex, efferent fibers of the vagus nerve transmit signals to the splenic nerve, which consists of sympathetic fibers, resulting in the release of norepinephrine within the spleen [161]. At the site of norepinephrine release, a population of memory $CD4^+$ T cells expressing β_2 -adrenergic receptors becomes activated and, in response, synthesizes and releases acetylcholine into the extracellular environment [162]. Acetylcholine then acts on macrophages expressing the $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor ($\alpha 7$ nAChR), leading to inhibition of LPS-induced pro-inflammatory cytokine production and consequently to attenuation of the systemic inflammatory response following exposure to infectious stimuli [156].

One of the primary experimental approaches for activating the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex *in vivo* is electrical stimulation of the vagus nerve, known as **Vagus Nerve Stimulation (VNS)** [163]. Many of the studies discussed below highlight the immunomodulatory effects of cholinergic signaling through the $\alpha 7$ nAChR, often mediated via activation of this reflex pathway.

A pivotal study first demonstrated that endothelial cells of human microvessels express the $\alpha 7$ nAChR. *In vivo* administration of nicotine or the cholinergic agonist CAP55 inhibited endothelial adhesion molecule expression in mice. Similarly, exposure of cultured human endothelial cells to acetylcholine or nicotinic agonists reduced TNF-induced expression of adhesion molecules, chemokine production, and leukocyte adhesion. These effects were mediated through $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation and subsequent inhibition of the NF- κ B signaling pathway. Finally, administration of cholinergic agonists or application of VNS suppressed leukocyte migration to sites of injury and inflammation *in vivo* [164].

Another study showed that VNS or nicotine administration (a nicotinic cholinergic receptor agonist) in mice reduced neutrophil migratory capacity by inhibiting expression of the adhesion molecule CD11b (β_2 -integrin) on their surface. This effect

occurred only in animals with an intact spleen, suggesting the involvement of the splenic component of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex [165].

Similarly, an *in vivo* model of systemic inflammation in mice demonstrated that vagotomy significantly delayed inflammation resolution by impairing the production and release of specialized pro-resolving lipid mediators—such as resolvins, protectins, lipoxins, and maresins [166,167].

Finally, in an *in vivo* model of endotoxemia in mice, cholinergic activation in the forebrain—via stimulation of the M1 muscarinic acetylcholine receptor (mAChR) and subsequent vagus nerve activation—led to decreased serum TNF- α levels. This finding suggests that the forebrain may serve as a higher regulatory center for the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex [168].

A substantial body of literature further supports the broad immunomodulatory effects of cholinergic signaling on immune cells, which merit detailed discussion by specific cell type.

Macrophages

Regarding the effects of cholinergic stimulation on macrophages, *in vitro* studies have shown that treatment of human macrophages stimulated with LPS results in a dose-dependent inhibition of TNF, IL-1 β , IL-6, and IL-18 secretion, without affecting the release of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10. *In vivo*, vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) in mice exposed to a lethal dose of LPS reduced TNF secretion from the spleen [163], an effect dependent on the presence of the $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor ($\alpha 7$ nAChR) [156].

Another study demonstrated that administration of nicotine to human macrophages stimulated with LPS or TNF- α inhibited the release of the proinflammatory cytokine **HMGB1 (high-mobility group box 1 protein)** through $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation and subsequent suppression of the NF- κ B signaling pathway. Furthermore, *in vivo* administration of nicotine in a murine sepsis model led to decreased circulating HMGB1 levels and improved survival rates [169].

In another study using *in vitro* cultures of murine peritoneal and human macrophages, as well as *in vivo* mouse experiments, administration of acetylcholine, the $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonist GTS-21, or VNS inhibited activation of the **NLRP3 inflammasome**, a molecular complex with strong proinflammatory activity. This effect was associated with suppression of mitochondrial DNA release from macrophages and a consequent decrease in IL-1 β , IL-18, and HMGB1 secretion, reflecting the anti-inflammatory potential of cholinergic $\alpha 7$ nAChR signaling [170].

Further evidence indicated that *in vivo* administration of GTS-21 in murine models of LPS-induced endotoxemia or acute kidney injury reduced systemic inflammation through $\alpha 7$ nAChR-mediated effects on splenic macrophages. *In vitro* stimulation of murine macrophage cell lines with LPS revealed that $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation enhanced intercellular interactions, leading to diminished proinflammatory cytokine production [171].

Additionally, nicotine administration in *in vitro* cultures of LPS-stimulated murine peritoneal macrophages suppressed TNF, MIP-2, and IL-6 expression through $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation and subsequent phosphorylation of the STAT3 transcription factor. In a related *in vivo* model of postoperative ileus in mice, VNS reduced

intestinal inflammation within the muscularis layer by inducing STAT3 activation in local macrophages adjacent to vagal efferent fibers, consistent with $\alpha 7$ nAChR-mediated cholinergic signaling. Consequently, VNS significantly decreased the incidence of postoperative ileus in mice [172].

Another study reported that nicotine treatment of human monocytes stimulated with LPS suppressed expression of the CD14 molecule (the LPS-binding receptor), Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4), the costimulatory molecule B7.1, CD40 (an essential costimulatory molecule for T-cell interactions), and TNF- α [173]. Similarly, nicotine exposure of human peripheral blood monocytes stimulated with IL-18—a proinflammatory cytokine involved in Th1 immune responses—reduced expression of adhesion and activation molecules (ICAM-1, B7.2, CD40) as well as production of IL-12, IFN- γ , and TNF- α . These inhibitory effects were mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation [174].

Nicotine has also been shown to exert suppressive effects on lymphocytic inflammatory activation and proliferation in a murine graft-versus-host disease model [175]. Moreover, nicotine administration in mice with experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) inhibited the migration of activated monocytes and neutrophils into the central nervous system by downregulating the expression of the chemotactic molecules CCL2 and CXCL2, via $\alpha 7$ nAChR and $\alpha 9$ nAChR signaling [176].

Additionally, nicotine treatment of **fibroblast-like synoviocytes (FLSs)** isolated from arthritic tissues of patients with rheumatoid arthritis resulted in a dose-dependent decrease in the production of proinflammatory cytokines IL-6 and MCP-1. This effect was mediated through activation of the **JAK2–STAT3 signaling pathway** following $\alpha 7$ nAChR stimulation [177].

Finally, administration of nicotine to macrophage cell lines derived from the respiratory system of mice infected with *Legionella pneumophila* enhanced bacterial replication within macrophages while reducing the production of proinflammatory cytokines IL-6, IL-12, and TNF- α . This effect was mediated via nicotinic receptors composed of $\alpha 4$ and $\alpha 2$ subunits [178].

Dendritic Cells

In the context of dendritic cells, one study reported that nicotine administration in cell cultures reduced their antigen uptake capacity. Under conditions of LPS stimulation, nicotine decreased the production of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-12, IL-1 β , and TNF- α , as well as IL-10. Moreover, in cocultures of dendritic cells with helper T lymphocytes, nicotine inhibited the antigen-induced activation of CD4⁺ T cells and the subsequent induction of a Th1-type immune response [179].

Another study demonstrated that treatment of human LPS-stimulated dendritic cells with nicotine suppressed T-cell proliferation and IFN- γ production, reduced HLA-DR expression, and promoted the release of Th2-type chemokines while suppressing Th1-associated responses [180]. Since nicotine is a potent agonist of the $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor ($\alpha 7$ nAChR), which is expressed on dendritic cells, these anti-inflammatory effects are likely mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation—mechanistically analogous to acetylcholine-induced modulation of the same receptor.

Further research showed that differentiation of human monocytes into dendritic cells in the presence of nicotine resulted in diminished expression of molecules essential

for antigen presentation. Under LPS stimulation, nicotine also reduced expression of the chemokine receptor CCR7—required for dendritic cell migration into lymphatic vessels—along with decreased IL-12 production and Th1 response induction [181]. Consistently, exposure of human dendritic cells to acetylcholine led to their differentiation toward a phenotype that promotes Th2 immune polarization by inducing the expression of the chemokines CCL22 and CCL17 [182].

In an *in vivo* murine model of inflammatory bowel disease, administration of **galantamine**, a centrally acting acetylcholinesterase inhibitor, or muscarinic receptor agonists attenuated intestinal mucosal inflammation. The data indicated that this occurred through activation of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex, originating from cholinergic centers in the CNS and mediated via the vagus and splenic nerves, ultimately leading to $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation on splenic dendritic cells. The result was a decrease in MHC class II expression and a reduction in proinflammatory cytokine production [183].

In a related study, administration of a selective central **M1 muscarinic receptor agonist (McN-A-343)** suppressed production of proinflammatory cytokines involved in Th1/Th17 immune responses in the colon and spleen of mice. This effect was mediated by $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation on splenic dendritic cells and subsequent inhibition of the NF- κ B signaling pathway [184].

Conversely, nicotine treatment at concentrations of 10^{-8} to 10^{-4} mol/L in human dendritic cell cultures increased expression of costimulatory and adhesion molecules, as well as MHC class II molecules. It also enhanced IL-12 production. These effects were blocked by broad-spectrum nicotinic antagonists, confirming mediation through nicotinic cholinergic receptor activation on dendritic cells. Mechanistically, this stimulatory action was linked to activation of the **PI3K, ERK, and p38 MAPK** signaling pathways. Furthermore, dendritic cells exposed to nicotine and peptide antigen demonstrated enhanced ability to stimulate T-cell proliferation and cytokine production [157].

The contradictory findings of this latter study compared to previous work may stem from differences in nicotine dosage, the absence of prior LPS stimulation of dendritic cells, and the use of peptide antigen in dendritic–T-cell cocultures. The variability in outcomes can also be attributed to activation of distinct intracellular signaling pathways under different experimental contexts. Thus, the presence or absence of an antigenic stimulus appears to condition dendritic cells toward a distinct transcriptional state, altering the nature of subsequent cholinergic modulation.

Another study found that acetylcholine treatment of human dendritic cells stimulated with IL-4 and GM-CSF upregulated the surface molecule **OX40L**, a key factor in promoting Th2 differentiation. This upregulation led to increased expression of Th2-associated chemokines (CCL22, CCL17) and cytokines (IL-4, IL-5, IL-13) by T lymphocytes in coculture [183].

Furthermore, an immunophenotypic analysis of splenic immune cells from mice with **experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE)** treated with nicotine during MOG immunization revealed that, although the numbers of peripheral dendritic and mononuclear cells remained unchanged, the expression of antigen presentation and costimulatory molecules (MHC class II, CD80, CD86) was markedly reduced. A corresponding analysis of CNS-infiltrating antigen-presenting cells during EAE

showed a significant reduction in their abundance, as well as decreased expression of costimulatory molecules and MHC class II [185].

Finally, it has been demonstrated that antigen-presenting cells derived from $\alpha 7$ nAChR-knockout mice exhibit impaired antigen-presentation capacity [154].

Lymphocytes

An initial *in vivo* study supports that vagus nerve stimulation in mice provokes a transient release of lymphocytes from the thymus—an effect prevented by vagotomy or by nicotinic receptor antagonists. This provides strong evidence that the CNS exerts regulatory control over the immune system [186]. Another study showed that in genetically modified mice lacking the $\alpha 7$ nAChR gene ($\alpha 7$ nAChR knockout, KO), immunization with a peptide antigen led to increased production of total and antigen-specific IgG1 antibodies by activated splenic cells, compared with controls. Proinflammatory cytokines TNF- α , IFN- γ , and IL-6 were also elevated in $\alpha 7$ nAChR-KO mice relative to wild-type animals. These findings suggest a potentially immunosuppressive role of $\alpha 7$ nAChR across both adaptive and innate immune functions [187]. In a similar vein, mice lacking M1/M5 muscarinic receptors exhibited reduced levels of total and antigen-specific IgG1 antibodies and decreased IL-6 after peptide antigen immunization, compared with wild-type mice [188].

T Lymphocytes

It has been reported that acetylcholine (ACh) produced endogenously by a leukemic human T-cell line and by cultured splenic cells from C57BL/6J mice acts autocrinely on nicotinic receptors expressed on their surface, inducing biochemical changes that increase IL-2 expression and thereby enhance proliferative capacity [189]. Another study showed that the surface profile of muscarinic and nicotinic ACh receptors on cultured murine CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells varies according to activation status (resting vs. TCR/CD3 engagement). Exposure to nicotine during TCR/CD3 stimulation markedly increased IFN- γ and suppressed IL-17 production, favoring a Th1 response over Th17. In contrast, muscarine under the same conditions increased IL-10 and IL-17 while suppressing IFN- γ , favoring Th2 and Th17 responses over Th1. These findings indicate that ACh exerts a context-dependent immunomodulatory role shaped by cellular activation state [190].

In a study using human peripheral blood, CD4⁺ T cells stimulated with ACh exhibited reduced cell numbers and suppression of IL-17, a cytokine central to Th17 differentiation [191]. Likewise, acetylcholinesterase inhibitors or nicotine, when added to *in vitro* cultures of mitogen-stimulated human T cells, significantly reduced proliferative capacity and the production of proinflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-1 β . The data implicated excess ACh acting through $\alpha 7$ nAChR on T cells [153]. Notably, the nonspecific cholinergic agonist carbamyl chloride (CC) mimicked ACh's antiproliferative effect at low concentrations; at higher concentrations, antagonism of muscarinic receptors was required to observe the same effect. This can be explained by the differing K_d values of mAChRs and nAChRs—nicotinic receptors are substantially more sensitive and thus activated by much lower agonist concentrations—whereas higher concentrations increasingly engage muscarinic receptors, which may promote T-cell activation and proliferation [192], [193], [194], [195].

Extending these findings *in vivo*, rivastigmine administration in a murine EAE model reduced proliferation of MOG-specific T cells and curtailed production of TNF- α and

IFN- γ . It also decreased IL-17 mRNA expression by ~80%, a cytokine implicated in multiple sclerosis pathogenesis. The proposed mechanism is that acetylcholinesterase inhibition elevates ACh levels, activating $\alpha 7$ nAChR on encephalitogenic T cells. Concomitantly, microglial activation was suppressed, and both infiltration and numbers of antigen-presenting macrophages in inflamed regions were reduced [196].

In the same context, nicotine administration in EAE mice first confirmed $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression on CD4⁺ T cells. Nicotine then reduced Th1-type (TNF- α , IFN- γ) and Th17-type (IL-17, IL-17F, IL-21, IL-22) cytokines, while increasing the Th2-promoting cytokine IL-4. Collectively, nicotine shifted immune polarization from Th1/Th17 toward Th2, consistent with ~50% suppression of the Th1 transcription factor T-bet and a ~350% increase of the Th2 transcription factor GATA-3 in CD4⁺ T cells [154]. Similarly, the selective $\alpha 7$ nAChR positive allosteric agonist **GAT107** reduced clinical disease severity in EAE, via dampening encephalitogenic T-cell proliferation, markedly reducing Th1/Th17 cytokines, and increasing IL-10. In parallel, GATA-3 expression rose (supporting Th2 differentiation), and both FoxP3 and TGF- β increased, indicating promotion and maturation of regulatory T cells [197].

A complementary set of experiments transferred encephalitogenic, MOG-specific T cells—capable of inducing EAE—from nicotine-treated or placebo-treated donor mice into healthy recipients. Recipients of T cells from nicotine-treated donors developed significantly milder disease, supporting a direct nicotine effect on T-cell function. Phenotyping of splenic lymphocytes from EAE mice exposed to nicotine during immunization versus placebo revealed substantial reductions in CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells and in B cells; Treg numbers were unchanged, but FoxP3 expression increased. Additional assays indicated that the reduced lymphocyte counts in nicotine-treated mice reflected impaired proliferation rather than increased cell death. Cytokine profiling showed clear reductions of IFN- γ and IL-2 from CD8⁺ T cells, unchanged IL-17, and increased IL-10 and TGF- $\beta 1$ —again consistent with a Th2-skewing effect at the expense of Th1. Finally, analysis of CNS-infiltrating lymphocytes during EAE showed marked reductions of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells and B cells in nicotine-treated animals [185].

Providing a different perspective, studies in the CEM human leukemic T-cell line showed that *in vitro* stimulation of M3 or M5 AChRs induces c-Fos protein, initiating a cascade that culminates in production of multiple immunomodulatory molecules and IL-2 gene expression in T cells [198]. Lastly, a review has noted that $\alpha 7$ nAChR stimulation on naïve Th cells can enhance their differentiation process [199].

B Lymphocytes

In cultures of B lymphocytes from Balb/c and C57Bl/6 mice, the presence of $\alpha 7$, $\alpha 4\beta 2$, and $\alpha 9\alpha 10$ nAChRs was initially demonstrated. During *in vitro* activation of B cells, expression of $\alpha 7$ and $\alpha 4\beta 2$ increased. Inhibition of $\alpha 7$ and $\alpha 9\alpha 10$ signaling led to a marked enhancement of CD40-mediated B-cell proliferation, whereas $\alpha 4\beta 2$ stimulation increased IgM-induced cellular proliferation. These findings indicate an underlying role for nicotinic cholinergic receptor activation in regulating B-cell immune functions [200]. Moreover, in BALB/c mice, both nicotine administration and VNS inhibited B-cell migration and reduced antibody production in response to pneumococcal infection. According to the study's data, this effect was mediated through agonism of $\alpha 7$ nAChR [201].

Microglia

Multiple studies highlight the role of cholinergic stimulation in microglia. In *in vitro* cultures of LPS/ATP-stimulated murine microglia and *in vivo* in EAE mice, administration of the $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonist PNU282987 reduced expression of β -arrestin-1, which drives activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome and associated pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and IL-18 in both experimental settings [202]. Another study examined chronic, continuous stress exposure in mice, which induced a pro-inflammatory profile—elevated IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-6 in brain and gastric tissues—and promoted a pro-inflammatory microglial phenotype. VNS in these mice decreased expression of these cytokines, suppressed activated microglial morphology, and improved clinical signs, with evidence that the beneficial effects were mediated via $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation on neuronal and microglial cells [203]. Additional work confirmed $\alpha 7$ nAChR expression on murine microglia and showed that pretreatment with acetylcholine or nicotine suppressed LPS-induced TNF- α release via $\alpha 7$ nAChR activation [158].

Further, nicotine enhanced COX-2 expression and prostaglandin E2 synthesis in LPS-stimulated murine microglia through $\alpha 7$ nAChR engagement [204]. Nicotine also facilitated P2X(7)-mediated TNF release—considered neuroprotective—while suppressing LPS-induced TNF release; this occurred through $\alpha 7$ nAChR-dependent modulation of TNF release (not production), indicating both neuroprotective and antineurotoxic roles for cholinergic $\alpha 7$ nAChR signaling in microglia [205]. In β -amyloid-stimulated microglia, nicotine reduced reactive oxygen species by inhibiting NADPH oxidase, again via $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonism [206]. Finally, in co-cultures of murine microglia and neurons, acetylcholine inhibited LPS-induced production of the pro-inflammatory mediators iNOS, TNF- α , and IL-1 β , and it prevented suppression of the neurotrophic factor IGF-1, with protection mediated through microglial $\alpha 7$ nAChR [207].

Human microglia also express muscarinic receptors responsive to cholinergic agonists [208]. Building on this, a subsequent study identified a human microglial subpopulation expressing the M3 muscarinic receptor. Culture with IFN- γ increased M3 expression and upregulated MHC-I and MHC-II. Administration of the M3 agonist carbachol reduced the phagocytic capacity of these microglia, underscoring cholinergic modulation of microglial immune functions [209].

Potential Immunomodulatory Role of Neurotransmitters in Multiple Sclerosis

Effects of Catecholamines in EAE and Multiple Sclerosis

A substantial body of research provides evidence for a disease-modifying influence of catecholamines in experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) and multiple sclerosis (MS). In this context, inhibition of the α_1 -adrenergic receptor with prazosin was examined in cultures of mononuclear cells derived from draining lymph nodes of mice during the inductive phase of EAE. The primary finding was suppression of proliferation of myelin basic protein (MBP)-specific CD4⁺ T cells. This effect appeared to result from prazosin-induced expansion of regulatory T cells and subsequent TGF- β production. Prazosin also decreased the number of antigen-presenting cells and reduced proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and IL-23, while increasing IL-10 levels—thus inhibiting Th17 differentiation of CD4⁺ T cells [210]. These findings align with earlier studies reporting that prazosin reduced clinical severity of EAE in Lewis rats [211–214].

Similarly, administration of the β -adrenergic receptor blocker **propranolol** during EAE induction in mice decreased disease severity and the number of mononuclear cells infiltrating the spinal cord during disease relapse. This effect was mediated via activation of microglial signaling pathways that suppressed proinflammatory cytokine production and promoted an anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective phenotype. Moreover, propranolol inhibited the reactivation and Th17 differentiation of CD4⁺ T cells during CNS infiltration [215].

Further evidence of sympathetic nervous system (SNS) involvement in MS was provided by a study showing that patients with active MS exhibited significantly lower plasma levels of epinephrine and norepinephrine compared to healthy controls and to patients in stable remission. The association between SNS dysfunction and chronic disease activity suggests a contribution to impaired immune regulation in MS [216]. Supporting this, chemical sympathectomy with **6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA)**—which induces transient degeneration of peripheral noradrenergic terminals—resulted in more severe EAE compared to controls [217]. However, this study did not consider that antigen-presenting cells themselves can produce norepinephrine, which facilitates T-cell activation and differentiation. Thus, disease exacerbation following sympathectomy may stem from the loss of norepinephrine's immunosuppressive influence during disease induction.

Conversely, administration of β -adrenergic agonists **isoproterenol** and **terbutaline** to mice immunized for EAE reduced the severity of the first clinical episode and decreased relapse frequency [218]. Likewise, isoproterenol treatment in Lewis rats immunized for EAE ameliorated disease severity, particularly when given from the time of immunization through the acute phase (days 8–14 post-immunization) [219]. Moreover, passively induced EAE—via transfer of lymph node cells (LNCs) from immunized Lewis rats—was more severe in chemically sympathectomized recipients than in intact controls. LNCs obtained from sympathectomized and immunized donors also caused more severe EAE in naïve recipients than cells from nonsympathectomized donors, demonstrating that loss of sympathetic innervation abolishes the immunosuppressive effects of catecholamines on neuroantigen-specific lymphocytes, rendering them more aggressive [220].

Building on this, the β_2 -adrenergic agonist **salbutamol** was administered orally to 21 patients with secondary progressive MS, based on prior findings that β_2 stimulation reduces IL-12 production by monocytes from healthy volunteers. Salbutamol significantly decreased IL-12 production by patient monocytes and dendritic cells, with effects persisting up to one week post-therapy [221]. Similarly, co-administration of the β_2 agonist **albuterol** with **glatiramer acetate** in patients with relapsing-remitting MS resulted in greater clinical improvement compared to glatiramer monotherapy [222]. Additionally, in a clinical study of patients presenting with clinically isolated syndrome (CIS), higher serum epinephrine levels were associated with reduced risk of relapse and fewer new MRI lesions [223].

Further studies demonstrated that administration of the β_2 agonist **clenbuterol** during the first three days of MOG immunization to induce EAE resulted in a milder clinical course than in controls, suggesting that clenbuterol's protective effect likely occurred by restricting the egress of autoreactive lymphocytes from lymph nodes rather than by suppressing CNS-infiltrating cells [84]. In another *in vivo* study, treatment of EAE mice with **L-DOPS** (a norepinephrine precursor) stabilized clinical scores, while co-administration with the norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor

atomoxetine significantly reduced disease severity. These effects were confined to the CNS, without altering peripheral Th1 or Th17 frequencies [224]. Furthermore, excessive sympathetic activation in genetically modified mice, followed by EAE induction, limited CD4⁺ T-cell differentiation and suppressed gene expression of proinflammatory cytokines IL-2, IFN- γ , and GM-CSF, yielding a milder clinical course. These effects were mediated via β_2 -adrenergic signaling [225].

Indirect evidence for norepinephrine's protective role in EAE and MS includes findings of decreased norepinephrine levels in the spinal cords of EAE mice [226,227] and in the CSF of MS patients [228], as well as reduced β -adrenergic receptor expression in white matter astrocytes from MS brains [229]. Interestingly, selective destruction of the **locus coeruleus (LC)** in mice prior to EAE induction resulted in a markedly milder disease course compared to controls [230]. Likewise, chemical depletion of norepinephrine stores before disease induction produced attenuated clinical manifestations [231,232].

From a different clinical perspective, administration of tricyclic and tetracyclic antidepressants combined with **L-DOPA**—which is converted to norepinephrine via dopamine β -hydroxylase—to 300 MS patients led to significant neurological improvement in 75% of cases within two months, affecting both sensory-motor and autonomic symptoms [233]. Similarly, combined administration of **active vitamin B₁₂**, **phenylalanine** (a norepinephrine precursor), and the norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor **lofepramine** improved clinical symptoms [234] and reduced the size and number of MRI lesions compared with controls [235]. Finally, a population-based study found that the β_2 agonist **fenoterol** was inversely associated with MS risk [236].

Taken together, the majority of studies support that **norepinephrine—particularly through β -adrenergic signaling—exerts immunosuppressive and neuroprotective effects**, improving clinical and pathological outcomes in EAE and showing therapeutic potential in MS. Reports suggesting milder disease following catecholamine depletion or β -blocker use appear contradictory; however, these typically involved catecholamine removal *prior* to disease induction. As previously noted, norepinephrine serves as a **costimulatory molecule** during CD4⁺ T-cell activation and differentiation; its absence during this phase would logically dampen immune activation. Nonetheless, it remains indisputable that catecholamines exert both **immunomodulatory and disease-modifying** influences in demyelinating disease—an area warranting further exploration given the pharmacological accessibility of their pathways and the wide availability of receptor-specific agonists for potential **therapeutic immunomodulation**.

Effects of Acetylcholine in EAE and Multiple Sclerosis

A substantial body of evidence indicates that acetylcholine (ACh) exerts disease-modifying effects both in experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) models and in patients with multiple sclerosis (MS). A clinical study quantified muscarinic cholinergic receptor density on CD4⁺ T lymphocytes among patients with chronic progressive MS, patients with stable MS, and healthy volunteers. Patients with chronic MS displayed significantly higher receptor densities compared with the other two groups, which did not differ from each other. This finding is consistent with lymphocyte hypersensitivity due to parasympathetic denervation or antigen-driven lymphocyte activation—two settings characterized by increased muscarinic receptor expression on lymphocytes [237]. In another study, NK cells engineered to express

choline acetyltransferase (ChAT), the enzyme that synthesizes acetylcholine, were delivered into the ventricles of mice with EAE. This reduced lesion development in brain and spinal cord, decreased infiltrating monocytes, and suppressed proinflammatory cytokine production—effects attributed to ACh acting on $\alpha 7$ nAChRs expressed by infiltrating monocytes, promoting their apoptosis [238].

Administration of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors to EAE mice produced a ~90% reduction in clinical disease severity, diminished infiltration of activated immune cells into the CNS, and reduced reactivity of CD4⁺ T cells to the encephalitogenic MOG_{35–55} peptide. These effects were attributed to increased availability of ACh engaging $\alpha 7$ nAChRs on CD4⁺ T cells [153], and were abrogated when $\alpha 7$ nAChR antagonists were co-administered in subsequent work [197]. Consistent with an impaired cholinergic brake in MS, ACh levels are significantly lower in serum and CSF of patients with RR-MS compared with healthy controls [239,240], while expression and enzymatic activity of the hydrolytic enzymes AChE and BChE are significantly increased in MS serum—associated with reduced ACh and elevated proinflammatory cytokines TNF α , IL-12/IL-23p40, and IL-18 [240]. In line with this, nicotine reduced IL-1 β and IL-17 expression in LPS-stimulated peripheral blood mononuclear cells from RR-MS patients via $\alpha 7$ nAChR signaling [241], suggesting that low endogenous ACh in MS may fail to activate $\alpha 7$ -mediated immunosuppression. Additionally, non-smoked tobacco use in MS patients has been associated with favorable disease effects, potentially through nicotine's action on $\alpha 7$ nAChRs and suppression of neuroinflammation [242].

Of particular interest, the muscarinic antagonist **benztropine** improved clinical scores in EAE whether given prophylactically at induction or therapeutically after onset, likely by enhancing oligodendrocyte-mediated remyelination and thereby accelerating repair of demyelinating lesions [243], with similar results reported subsequently [244]. Selective $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonism with **PNU-282987** likewise improved clinical severity and reduced CNS inflammatory infiltration in EAE [245]. **Nicotine** also ameliorated EAE clinical scores via $\alpha 7$ and $\alpha 9$ nAChR signaling [176].

A different approach showed that the “silent agonist” **m-bromo-PEP** at $\alpha 7$ nAChRs and the nonselective noncompetitive nicotinic antagonist **mecamylamine** both improved EAE outcomes, apparently by lowering expression of chemotactic and adhesion molecules and thereby limiting CNS infiltration. These agents appeared to stabilize $\alpha 7$ nAChR in conformations that do not open the ion channel, implying that $\alpha 7$ -mediated immunomodulation can occur independent of ion flux [246].

Consistently, the $\alpha 7$ -selective positive allosteric agonist **GAT107** reduced EAE severity by dampening CNS inflammation through inhibition of encephalitogenic T-cell proliferation [198].

Not all findings are uniform: in $\alpha 7$ nAChR-deficient mice, EAE onset, clinical scores, and lesion composition were not different from wild-type, and $\alpha 7$ expression did not correlate with reductions in TNF α , IL-1 β , or IL-18 [247]. Moreover, left cervical vagotomy in EAE mice—blunting ACh release—improved clinical symptoms and decreased IL-6, IL-4, IL-17, and IFN γ , possibly reflecting ACh's costimulatory role in splenic CD4⁺ T-cell proliferation and differentiation during antigen priming [248] and/or a proinflammatory contribution of $\alpha 9$ nAChR signaling [249]. In support of the latter, inducing Th17 cells lacking ChAT (and thus endogenous ACh synthesis) yielded milder EAE and reduced CNS immune infiltration, highlighting a potential costimulatory role of ACh in Th17 activation/differentiation [250].

Therapeutically, **rivastigmine** (an AChE inhibitor) markedly reduced EAE clinical signs and disease-related memory deficits, decreased demyelination, microglial proinflammatory activation, and axonal injury—consistent with suppressed reactivity of encephalitogenic T cells and reduced TNF- α , IFN- γ , and IL-17 production [197]. **Nicotine** administration reduced clinical symptoms, limited CNS infiltration by activated monocytes and CD4⁺ T cells, lessened tissue damage, and enhanced neuronal survival; these benefits occurred independently of corticosteroids, as adrenalectomized mice responded similarly [154]. Follow-up work showed diminished nicotine efficacy in α 7 nAChR knockout mice and implicated additional nicotinic subtypes in the immunosuppressive mechanism [159]. Exposure to nicotine also delayed and blunted autoimmune responses to myelin antigens, producing a milder clinical course [185].

Genetic deletion of the **α 9 nAChR** subunit delayed onset and reduced EAE severity, implicating α 9 nAChRs as pro-inflammatory mediators via endogenous ACh; **nicotine** reduced disease activity in wild-type mice. Since nicotine antagonizes α 9 nAChRs but ACh is an agonist [251], these data support a model whereby nicotine's benefits derive from **agonism at α 7** and **antagonism at α 9** nAChRs. Nicotine also ameliorated EAE in **β 2 nAChR** knockout mice, although β 2-deficient animals showed impaired recovery irrespective of treatment, suggesting β 2-mediated cholinergic signaling contributes to neurorepair processes [249]. In double-knockout α 9/ α 10 mice, the α 9 subunit again emerged as the driver of EAE exacerbation, with α 10 absence having no effect [252].

Additional studies show nicotine reduces demyelination, restores weight, and suppresses microglial proinflammatory activation in EAE [253]; synergizes with **mesenchymal progenitor cell** transplantation to further improve clinical and histopathological outcomes while increasing IL-10 and decreasing IL-17 and TNF- α from splenocytes [254]; promotes proliferation/survival of myelin-producing **oligodendrocytes** within spinal cord lesions [255]; and **donepezil** (AChE inhibitor) improves EAE clinical and pathological parameters [256].

In summary, the preponderance of evidence indicates that acetylcholine—particularly through **α 7 nAChR** engagement—confers meaningful clinical benefit in EAE, setting the stage for clinical trials in MS to determine translational efficacy in humans. These findings also prompt reflection on widely used drugs (e.g., acetylcholinesterase inhibitors) that may harbor **unappreciated immunomodulatory effects** relevant to demyelinating disease.

Epilogue

This review collates evidence for neural-immune crosstalk between the central nervous system (CNS) and lymphoid organs, and for the expression of norepinephrine (NE) and acetylcholine (ACh) receptors on immune cells—the principal neurotransmitters of the autonomic nervous system. Together, these findings establish a mechanistic basis for bidirectional communication between the CNS and the immune system. Convergent studies indicate that NE is predominantly immunosuppressive—chiefly via β ₂-adrenergic receptor stimulation—when superimposed on pre-existing immune activation by infectious stimuli, yet can be immunostimulatory when present during the **induction** phase of immune activation. Likewise, accumulating data support an immunosuppressive role of ACh through the α 7 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (α 7 nAChR), particularly in the context of prior immune stimulation. The **cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex**, which integrates

both NE and ACh signaling, further constrains excessive immune activation. Finally, numerous preclinical and clinical observations point to disease-modifying effects of these neurotransmitters—and of agonists at their receptors—in multiple sclerosis (MS) and experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE), with the preponderance of evidence favoring beneficial actions in these conditions.

Given the existence of a neural circuitry modulating immunity, key questions arise regarding CNS control centers with condition-dependent immunoregulatory roles (e.g., the **locus coeruleus**). Similarly, the point of origin and therapeutic harnessing of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex warrant investigation, including whether medically induced activation can benefit states of sepsis or autoimmunity. Accepting the immunomodulatory roles of NE and ACh also compels systematic study of commonly used therapeutics—vasopressor NE infusions in septic or hypovolemic shock, β -agonists and β -blockers, acetylcholinesterase inhibitors, and nicotine patches—for potential secondary immune effects, an area that is both clinically relevant and experimentally tractable.

Conclusions

1. **Established neural-immune interface.** Neurotransmitter receptors on immune cells and autonomic neural connections between the CNS and primary/secondary lymphoid organs are unequivocally present, implying direct CNS control of immune function and motivating work to localize and characterize the responsible brain centers.
2. **Dual role of NE.** Norepinephrine suppresses immunity via β_2 -adrenergic signaling once the immune system is activated, yet serves as a **costimulatory** signal necessary during antigen presentation and T-cell priming.
3. **Chronic stress and immune suppression.** Chronic stress elevates catecholamines and glucocorticoids, fostering a persistent state of immunosuppression that may predispose to autoimmunity and tumorigenesis. This raises the question of whether **β -blockers** could beneficially modulate such states.
4. **Acute stress after stroke/MI.** Acute cerebrovascular events or myocardial infarction trigger intense sympathetic activation and are frequently followed by infections—especially respiratory. It is plausible that a catecholamine “immunosuppressive surge” facilitates these infections, suggesting a potential role for **β -blockade** in mitigating them.
5. **Cancer milieu.** Malignancy is accompanied by elevated catecholamines; tumors may exploit this to induce immunosuppression and facilitate progression. **β -blockers** could, therefore, act as adjuvants to chemotherapy, as suggested by emerging studies.
6. **Asthma therapies and MS exacerbations.** Given the central role of **Th17** responses in MS pathophysiology, widely used **β -agonists** for asthma—if they bias toward Th17—could theoretically increase relapse risk in patients with both diseases. Notably, asthma appears more prevalent in MS than in

the general population. A targeted study comparing relapse rates in MS alone versus MS+asthma on β -agonists would be informative.

7. **Locus coeruleus as a hub.** The locus coeruleus is the primary CNS source of NE. Its destruction accelerates dopaminergic neurodegeneration in Parkinsonian models and worsens EAE when ablation occurs after induction. These effects may reflect loss of NE's immunosuppressive actions within the CNS; imaging-detectable LC injury might therefore prognosticate disease trajectories.
8. **Stress, priming, and MS relapses.** NE contributes costimulation during induction of both Th1 and Th2 responses, and absence of NE during EAE induction yields milder disease. This supports the concept that MS relapses temporally linked to psychosocial stress stem from sympathetic overactivity and consequent dysregulated immune priming.
9. **Synergy with S1PR1 modulation.** Fingolimod (S1PR1 modulation) limits egress of autoreactive lymphocytes from lymph nodes. **β -agonists** likewise restrict lymphocyte egress and ameliorate EAE when given post-induction. This suggests potential **therapeutic synergy** between β -agonists and fingolimod in MS.
10. **Therapeutic neuromodulation.** Rigorous studies should assess whether activating the **cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex**—via selective nicotinic agonists or **vagus nerve stimulation (VNS)**—benefits MS relapses and other systemic inflammatory diseases, and define optimal stimulation paradigms.
11. **AChE inhibitors as immunomodulators.** Given ACh's $\alpha 7$ nAChR-mediated immunosuppression, acetylcholinesterase inhibitors used in dementia and myasthenia gravis may exert **unrecognized immunomodulatory effects**. It is worth determining to what extent their clinical benefits derive from immune modulation versus classical cholinergic mechanisms.

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